

**PERMANENT FORMWORK OF TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE (TRC) FOR
COMPOSITE CONCRETE SLABS**

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ABSTRACT

This work proposes a new system of composite slabs consisting of a permanent Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC) formwork (TRC deck) with a trapezoidal section. A methodology for the design of composite slabs is presented and validated with experimental data. Finally, the methodology is used to design and conduct a parametric study based on the proposed system of composite slabs in this work. The results indicated that the design methodology was able to estimate the load-carrying capacity of the composite slabs subjected to bending with average errors of 10%. The use of TRC deck presents great potential, with an average increase in flexural load capacity of 10% due to variations in geometry and average increases of 113.3% and 302.3% when going from 2 layers of FRP reinforcement to 3 and from 2 to 4 layers, respectively.

KEYWORDS

Textile reinforced concrete (TRC); stay-in-place formwork; composite slab; TRC deck;

INTRODUCTION

Construction management has always focused on minimizing two interrelated factors: construction duration and the total cost (life cycle) of a structure. Stay-In-Place (SIP) formwork elements, also known as permanent or integrated elements, serve this purpose by allowing the development of hybrid concrete construction practices that combine the benefits of precast concrete, such as speed, controlled quality, precision, and impeccable finishing, with the advantages of on-site construction, such as cost savings, continuity, and robustness. SIP formwork is a structural element used to contain and shape the placed concrete and remain in place throughout the lifespan of the structure.

In this regard, the use of SIP elements in the production of composite concrete slabs offers several advantages. By eliminating construction steps (e.g., formwork and shoring assembly and disassembly, reinforcement cutting and bending), indirect costs can be reduced. Enhanced mechanical performance can also be achieved through a rationalization/industrialization process in construction, which provides stricter quality control. Additionally, the system presents environmental and aesthetic advantages by producing less waste and eliminating the need for finishing the underside of the slabs.

Several SIP formwork systems have been developed, incorporating materials such as steel, wood, and fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP) (Gai et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2010; De Sutter et al., 2014; Goyal et al., 2016; Pournasiri et al., 2022). Recently, the research group "Composite Materials for Resilient and Sustainable Structures - CMRSS" at the University of Brasília proposed a system of slabs based on an FRP SIP formwork, referred to as "FRP deck" (Souza & Lameiras, 2023). However, these systems have the disadvantage of being highly susceptible to corrosion and/or having low fire resistance (Michel et al., 2019).

The use of Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC) emerges as an innovative solution because the material used for manufacturing these forms can offer advantages compared to SIP systems made of other materials due to the incorporation of corrosion-resistant reinforcement in a thin-walled cementitious product with high load-carrying capacity (Brameshuber et al., 2004). The fibers composing the textile strands are made from high-strength materials with relatively high modulus of elasticity compared to other materials. These fibers are mostly produced by extrusion of various materials, such as glass, basalt, aramid, carbon, polyamide, and polypropylene. Subsequently, the fibers are combined into cords that can be twisted into strands or woven, providing flexibility in textile meshes and allowing the design of

thin SIP formwork elements with complex geometry. The length of these fibers can reach hundreds of meters, practically without length limitations in production (Peled et al., 2017).

TRC has already been successfully used for structural strengthening of existing structures (Peled et al., 2017; H. Y. Kim et al., 2021), and in this regard, an American standard, ACI 549.6R (2020), provides recommendations for the use and design of TRC as reinforcement. Nevertheless, TRC has also been employed in the production of new structures (Curbach et al., 2007; Hegger et al., 2011; Shams et al., 2014; Scholzen et al., 2015).

Notably, a group of researchers from the University of Patras in Greece conducted a study exploring the production of composite slabs using TRC SIP formwork (Papantoniou et al., 2012). However, the investigation focused on a deck with relatively simple geometry, having a rectangular section, and using steel reinforcement inserted in the deck (to enhance strength, alter the failure mechanism, and increase stiffness). Additionally, the authors incorporated specific transverse beams at the edges to increase the slabs' horizontal and vertical shear strength, thereby modifying the failure mode (breaking only by flexure).

Therefore, this work aims to present a new system of composite slabs based on the use of a TRC deck for residential and commercial buildings, called TRC deck. The proposed deck has a trapezoidal cross-section with a theoretical span of 2.55 meters. After introducing the new TRC deck, this work presents a proposed methodology for flexural design. This methodology is validated using literature data, and finally, a parametric study is conducted to assess the impact of geometry changes and the number of TRC layers on the load-carrying capacity of the slabs.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Concrete composite slabs refer to structural systems in which concrete elements and other materials are combined to form a load-bearing structure. In this specific case, the TRC permanent formwork is used as an integral part of the slab.

Therefore, the composite slab was theoretically analyzed using a simplified one-dimensional structural model and the transformed section method by Timoshenko. The compatibility of deformations between elements and the principle of internal force equilibrium were taken into consideration. The behavior of the TRC formwork was treated as linear elastic, while the concrete was considered as nonlinear elastic. This approach will allow for a more accurate analysis of the structural performance of the composite slab.

ACI 549.6R (2020) provides guidelines based on ACI CODE-318-19(22): Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary (Reapproved 2022) for the design of TRC-reinforced beams. Therefore, the design of the composite slabs was obtained based on the proposed model for beams, with appropriate adaptations. This means that the resistance capacity is reduced by a safety factor determined based on the expected failure mode. Thus, in this study, the calculations of the resistance capacity of the composite slabs using the TRC technique were performed with and without the application of the reduction factors indicated in the design codes, in order to obtain design values and simulate the results obtained in the laboratory.

The evaluation of the resistance capacity of the cross section by the TRC technique was carried out following the guidelines of the American standard ACI 549.6R (2020), referring to beams, with the necessary adaptations. The representation of the balance of forces in a composite element of concrete with TRC can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Force equilibrium of a section of the TRC/concrete composite slab.

Recommends starting the calculation process of the reinforcement system by determining the strain in the concrete substrate at the time of reinforcement application (ϵ_{bi}). However, in order to adapt the model for TRC/concrete composite slabs with the use of permanent TRC formwork, there will be no deformation of the substrate as it is not a reinforcement. This is because the concrete will be poured onto the formwork, meaning that the TRC formwork will be concreted beforehand, allowing for a 28-day curing period. Therefore, for this model, the strain in the concrete substrate will be assumed as zero ($\epsilon_{bi} = 0$).

The first step of the design process was to establish an initial position for the neutral axis (c). The ACI 440.2R (2017) standard recommends that, in the first iteration, the depth of the neutral axis should be equal to 0.2 times the effective height (d) of the beam. This allows for the calculation of the effective strain in the TRC formwork (ϵ_{fe}) using Equation 1, where ϵ_{cu} represents the ultimate strain of the concrete, which has a value of 3‰, and d_f represents the distance from the top fiber of the element to the centroid of the TRC formwork.

$$\epsilon_{fe} = \epsilon_{cu} \left(\frac{d_f - c}{c} \right) - \epsilon_{bi} \leq \epsilon_{fd} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Therefore, it is necessary to verify compliance with the requirement proposed by the model, in which the effective deformation of the TRC formwork is not greater than the ultimate deformation obtained through direct tensile testing of the TRC. If the requirement is not met ($\epsilon_{fd} \leq \epsilon_{fe}$), adopt $\epsilon_{fe} = \epsilon_{fd}$.

According to the recommendation of ACI 549.6R (2020) standard, the deformations of the longitudinal reinforcement in steel (ϵ_s) and in concrete (ϵ_c), as well as the stress in the longitudinal reinforcement (f_s), are calculated, as shown in Equations 2 to 4.

$$\epsilon_s = (\epsilon_{fe} + \epsilon_{bi}) \cdot \left(\frac{d-c}{h-c} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\epsilon_c = (\epsilon_{fe} + \epsilon_{bi}) \cdot \left(\frac{c}{h-c} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$f_s = E_s \cdot \epsilon_s \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Next, the calculation of the stress in the reinforcement system (f_{fe}) is performed, as shown in Equation 5.

$$f_{fe} = E_f \cdot \epsilon_{fe} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

After determining the stresses and deformations in the longitudinal reinforcement and the TRC formwork, the equilibrium conditions of the section are checked. These conditions are calculated using Equations 6 to 9, where ϵ_c represents the maximum deformation of the concrete, ϵ_c is the deformation of the unconfined concrete, E_c is the modulus of elasticity of the concrete, and A_s is the area of the existing longitudinal reinforcement cross-section.

$$\varepsilon'_c = \frac{1,7 \cdot f'_c}{E_c} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{4 \cdot \varepsilon'_c - \varepsilon_c}{6 \cdot \varepsilon'_c - 2 \cdot \varepsilon_c} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{3 \cdot \varepsilon'_c \cdot \varepsilon_c - \varepsilon_c^2}{3 \cdot \beta_1 \cdot \varepsilon_c'^2} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$c = \frac{A_s \cdot f_s + A_f \cdot f_{fe}}{\alpha_1 \cdot f'_c \cdot \beta_1 \cdot b} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

When verifying that the initially established neutral axis depth (c) differs from the one obtained in the design, a new depth for the neutral axis is assigned, and new calculations are performed until the calculated position of the neutral axis matches the initially assumed position. To determine convergence in the analysis, it is recommended to set a criterion where the difference between the neutral axis values is equal to 1×10^{-5} m.

Upon completing the calculation procedure for the Ultimate Limit State (ULS) analysis, the nominal resisting moment (M_n) of the composite TRC/concrete slab is determined using Equation 10. This moment is composed of the sum of the nominal moment resisted by the reinforcement (M_{ns}) and by the TRC formwork (M_{nf}), as presented in Equations 11 and 12, respectively.

$$M_n = M_{ns} + M_{nf} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$M_{ns} = A_s \cdot f_s \left(d - \frac{\beta_1 \cdot c}{2} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$M_{nf} = A_f \cdot f_{fe} \cdot \left(d_f - \frac{\beta_1 \cdot c}{2} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

The reduction factor (ϕ), as presented in Equation 13, is determined based on the steel deformation (ε_s) and the steel yield deformation (ε_{sy}). When $\varepsilon_s = 6.60\%$, which is higher than the reference value of 5% , the value of ϕ is equal to 0.90 .

$$\phi = \begin{cases} 0,90 & \text{if } \varepsilon_s \geq 0,005 \\ 0,65 + \frac{0,25 \cdot (\varepsilon_s - \varepsilon_{sy})}{0,005 - \varepsilon_{sy}} & \text{if } \varepsilon_{sy} < \varepsilon_s < 0,005 \\ 0,65 & \text{if } \varepsilon_s \leq \varepsilon_{sy} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

The ultimate moment (M_u) is calculated by multiplying the resisting moment (M_n) by the reduction factor (ϕ), as shown in Equation 14.

$$M_u = \phi \cdot M_n \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

In this sense, to feed the analytical model, it is necessary to obtain the maximum stress and strain of the TRC, as well as the modulus of elasticity. Therefore, through the experimental results obtained in the TRC direct traction test, it is possible to obtain the stress (σ_t). After that, the stress is divided by the cross-sectional area of the specimen (A_{TRC}), in order to obtain the maximum force (F_{max}), as shown in Equation 15.

$$F_{max} = \frac{\sigma_t}{A_{TRC}} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

After obtaining the maximum force, the force is divided by the fiber area (A_f) in order to obtain the maximum stress of the TRC ($\vartheta_{tex,max}$), as shown in Equation 16.

$$\vartheta_{tex,max} = \frac{F_{max}}{Af} \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

To obtain the modulus of elasticity of the TRC, it is necessary to divide the maximum stress of the TRC ($\vartheta_{tex,max}$) by the maximum strain obtained in the direct tensile test, as shown in Equation 17.

$$E_{tex} = \frac{\vartheta_{tex,max}}{\varepsilon_{tex}} \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

VALIDATION OF THE ANALYTICAL MODEL

The results of the experimental study conducted by Papantoniou et al. (2012) allow for the evaluation of the expected resistance capacity obtained through design models. In this regard, two elements were chosen to be studied, referred to as Type B and Type C, with Type B being a beam with a thickness of 333 mm and Type C being a slab with a width of 1000 mm, as observed in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Specimens studied by Papantoniou et al. (2012) (all units in mm).

All Type B and C elements, as well as the elements used in the parametric analysis, used the same setup, as shown in Figure 2, with a theoretical span corresponding to 2550 mm, and the distance between the load application point and the support axis (L_s) equal to 850 mm.

Figure 2. Setup used by Papantoniou et al. (2012) (all units in mm).

Steel reinforcement of the in-situ concrete topping was of B500C class (520 MPa and 621 MPa, yield point and tensile strength, respectively). A welded wire mesh (B500A \varnothing 4.2/150 mm with 634 MPa and 658 MPa, yield point and tensile strength, respectively) was positioned in the compression zone of Type B and Type C specimens. The mean compressive and flexural strengths and modulus of elasticity for both mortar mixtures at an age of 90 days (when the majority of tests was performed) were equal to 12 MPa, 60 MPa and 23 GPa, respectively. The mean compressive and splitting tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the in-situ concrete at an age of 28 days (in-situ concreting took place 28 days prior to testing) was equal to 28 MPa, 2.6 MPa and 24 GPa, respectively.

The position of the tensile strength of fabrics (F_{te}) was adopted considering the centroid of the rectangular section in order to simplify the model, as shown in Figure 1. Thus, the assumption is made that all fibers are positioned at half the thickness of the rectangular section (a single volume) to obtain the resultant. Additionally, it is considered that there is perfect bond at the TRC/Concrete interface.

All specimen construction parameters are given in Table 1. Specimens receive the following notation: T_M_S_L(c), where T stands for the specimen Type (B or C); M stands for the textile fibrous material [GI, GII, CI, CII and CIII, as per Figure 3 – superscript FS (for Type C specimens only) denotes the use of finely graded sand]; S stands for the steel reinforcement scheme (where applicable, as in XØY, X being the number of bars and Y their diameter); and L stands for the number of textile layers in the TRC formwork (1, 2, 3 or 4). The indication “c” (where is applicable) which follows the number of textile layers notation denotes that the textile reinforcement is polymer-coated by hand.

Figure 3. Mechanical properties – only FRP mesh - Papantoniou et al. (2012)

For specimens in group B, all specimens with Glass fiber TRC formworks failed due to textile reinforcement rupture that followed the yielding of steel reinforcement exception being the specimens receiving Ø4.2 rebars, which failed due to steel bar rupture. As for group C, all specimens failed due to textile reinforcement rupture following steel reinforcement yielding. Textile reinforcement rupture for specimen C_III^{FS}_6Ø8_3Lc was accompanied by spalling of matrix cover.

Finally, after obtaining and inputting the data into the analytical model, it was possible to obtain the results, as shown in Figure 5, which displays the curves of Force (F) versus vertical displacement (mm) of the evaluated beams/slabs, with the experimental curves and dashed lines representing the load obtained via the analytical model. Table 1 summarizes the results of the forces obtained analytically and experimentally.

Figure 4: Force vs vertical displacement curves. Adapted from de Papantoniou et al. (2012)

Table 1: Summary of the ultimate load results obtained in the experimental test/analytical model

Specimen	Fibrous Material	N° of Layers	Vf (%)	Fiber Area (mm ²)	Steel Area (mm ²)	Max Load Exp. (kN)	Max. Load Analytical ACI (kN)	Fexp/Fu
B GI 4Φ4.2 2L	E-Glass	2	4.96	41.29	55.418	16.50	13.446	1.227
B GI 2Φ8 2L	E-Glass	2	4.96	41.29	100.531	19.50	18.594	1.049
B GI 2Φ10 2L	E-Glass	2	4.96	41.29	157.080	26.00	24.905	1.044
B GI 4Φ4.2 3L	E-Glass	3	7.44	61.94	55.418	17.50	15.775	1.109
B GI 2Φ8 3L	E-Glass	3	7.44	61.94	100.531	22.50	20.890	1.077
B GI 2Φ10 3L	E-Glass	3	7.44	61.94	157.080	30.50	27.160	1.123
B GII 2Φ8 3L	E-Glass	3	11.04	91.91	100.531	31.50	28.574	1.102
B CI 2Φ8 2L	Carbon	2	7.68	63.94	100.531	31.00	26.909	1.152
B CII 2Φ8 2LC	Carbon	2	3.84	31.97	100.531	29.00	20.674	1.403
C_CIII_FS_6Φ8_3LC	Carbon	3	5.76	144.00	301.593	104.00	92.458	1.125
C CIII_FS_6Φ8_3L	Carbon	3	5.76	144.00	301.593	76.00	70.059	1.085
C CIII 6Φ8 3L	Carbon	3	5.76	144.00	301.593	88.00	92.900	0.947
Control	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	301.593	48.00	41.191	1.165

By analyzing the data provided in Table 1 and Figure 4, it can be observed that the analytical model is able to predict values of the last acceptable load, even with the use of a simplified model, average variation of 10%, when compared to the sensitivity of the model to analyze elements with 2 and 3 layers, from group A and B. Regarding the elements from group C, it is noticed that when using a rectangular geometry, the model presented a sensitivity with an average variation of 5%, being able to relate this positive result due to the geometry of the element approaching a representation of the cross section of a beam, after all, the applied model derives from an adaptation of the beam model, that is, as the complexity of the section increases, the variations of the results obtained with the model in question. The results of the experimental tests are within a range that allows variation in strength; However, it is worth mentioning that in the experimental study only 1 specimen was tested for each layer variation, making it impossible to capture the variation and the standard deviation between the tests. Regarding the failure mode, the simplified model considered bending as the predominant failure mode. In this sense, it was assumed that there is perfect adherence in the TRC/Concrete interface.

The beams/slabs studied by Papantoniou et al. (2012) used a rectangular geometry with the insertion of ribs to increase stiffness and contribute to the reduction of vertical displacement under loading. Nevertheless, the authors chose to incorporate longitudinal bars (B500C class - 520 MPa and 621 MPa, yield point and tensile strength, respectively) along the section of the elements in order to alter the failure mode (as the steel always yields before the fibers, providing a warning before the structural member fails, since the fibers exhibit brittle behavior with sudden failure) and increase the stiffness of the element.

PROPOSAL FOR A NEW COMPOSITE SLAB SYSTEM WITH TRC DECK

Considering the studies conducted by Papantoniou et al. (2012) and the presented analytical model, a new geometry was developed without the insertion of longitudinal bars to assess the ultimate capacity. The proposed geometry is trapezoidal, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Proposal for a new geometry for feasibility study

The position of the tensile strength of fabrics (F_{fe}) was adopted considering the geometric center of the trapezoidal section to simplify the model. Thus, the assumption is made that all fibers are positioned at this point (a single volume) to obtain the vector. Additionally, it is considered that there is perfect bond at the TRC/Concrete interface, with the predominant failure mode being bending.

In the analyzed geometry, the thickness of the TRC deck of 25 mm was considered. This deck has two height options, namely 60 mm and 80 mm (with variation in the number of layers), both resulting in a total slab height of 150 mm, as shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. All input data relating to material properties (concrete/TRC/FRP) were assumed to be the same as those proposed by Papantoniou et al. (2012), cited above.

Figure 6: Cross-section of TRC formwork (all units in mm)

Figure 7: Cross-section of TRC formwork with variation in the number of layers (all units in mm)

By analyzing the data provided in Table 2, it can be observed that the results demonstrate that the trapezoidal geometry with 4 layers obtained significant strength values compared to the values obtained in the study conducted by Papantoniou et al. (2012) – a study that includes the contribution of longitudinal reinforcement, which was not adopted in the proposed geometry. In the analysis in question, assume that all elements fail by flexion, is governed by fiber rupture.

Table 2: Summary of the results of the ultimate loads obtained for the new geometry/analytical model

Specimen	Fibrous Material	N° of Layers	Vf (%)	Fiber Area (mm ²)	Max. Load Analytical (kN)	Moment (kN.m)
Z_CIII_2L_80	Carbon	2	3.840	82.66	12.570	5.294
Z_CII_3L_80	Carbon	3	5.760	123.99	26.678	11.338
Z_CII_4L_80	Carbon	4	7.680	165.32	50.269	21.364
Y_GI_2L_80	E-Glass	2	4.961	106.80	15.088	6.412
Y_GI_3L_80	E-Glass	3	7.442	160.20	20.728	8.809
Y_GI_4L_80	E-Glass	4	9.923	213.60	26.680	11.339
Z_CIII_2L_60	Carbon	2	3.840	82.66	13.525	5.748
Z_CII_3L_60	Carbon	3	5.760	123.99	28.989	12.32
Z_CII_4L_60	Carbon	4	7.680	165.32	54.740	23.264
Y_GI_2L_60	E-Glass	2	4.961	106.80	16.378	6.961
Y_GI_3L_60	E-Glass	3	7.442	160.20	22.510	9.567
Y_GI_4L_60	E-Glass	4	9.923	213.60	28.991	12.321

The number of layers directly affects the resistance capacity, and it is possible to observe an average increase of 113.3% when comparing elements with 2 and 3 layers, and 302.3% when comparing elements with 2 and 4 layers, for carbon fibers. Regarding glass fibers, there was an average gain of 37.4% when comparing elements with 2 and 3 layers, and 76.9% for elements with 2 and 4 layers. However, it is worth noting that the results obtained from the direct tensile tests conducted by Papantoniou et al. (2012) showed an inversely proportional relationship between resistance capacity and material deformation. In other words, as the number of layers in the TRC increases, there is a significant increase in resistance capacity, but there is a loss in material deformation capacity of approximately 30%.

Regarding the results obtained between the specimens Y_GI_2L_80 and Z_CIII_2L_80, it can be observed that the higher resistance capacity was obtained for the glass fiber, however, this is directly related to the fiber volume, as it can be analyzed that the specimen with carbon fibers has 22.5% less volume when compared to the specimen with glass fibers.

Two heights were defined for the TRC deck forms, aiming to seek alternatives for improving vertical displacement, which is related to the Serviceability Limit State (SLS). However, the SLS will not be discussed in this study, as it will be the focus of future research. Regarding the resistance capacity, it can be observed that the 60 mm forms showed higher resistance gains, around 8%, when compared to the 80 mm forms, and this is directly related to the adopted design model, as the distance between the upper fiber of the slab and the centroid of the TRC form (d_f) directly influences the resistance gain when examining the equations. In other words, the greater the distance, the greater the resistance gain. Therefore, the 60 mm and 80 mm TRC forms have the following values for d_f : 120.131 mm and 110.85 mm, respectively.

Regarding the new proposal, it is known the importance of raising questions about possible problems related to the stress concentration in the corners, as well as the shear resistance capacity in the inclined web. All these questions are important and will be evaluated later with the continuity of the project, through experimental tests. Thus, making it possible to obtain more in-depth analyzes on the element.

CONCLUSIONS

The present analytical model, despite being a simplified model, allowed for the prediction of the ultimate load, providing greater clarity regarding design in the Ultimate Limit State (ULS). Therefore, the conclusions cited below are a perspective.

By increasing the number of layers in the TRC, it was possible to observe an average increase of 300% in the resistance capacity of the materials, comparing the elements with 2 and 4 layers, with carbon fibers. Regarding the glass fibers, there was an average gain of 76.9%, comparing the elements with 2 and 4 layers. In this sense, it is possible to conclude that carbon fibers have greater resistance capacity compared to glass fibers, provided they have the same volume of fibers.

The new proposed geometry exhibited a good load capacity, with an average value of 50 kN, achieved by using 4 layers of carbon fibers without adding steel bars to the concrete, with a formwork height of 80 mm. The 60 mm formwork showed a higher load capacity compared to the 80 mm formwork; however, reducing this height may have a negative impact on the SLS analyses. Therefore, based on the obtained predictions, it is worth emphasizing the need to continue the studies in order to verify the values later after conducting the experimental tests. Regarding the number of layers, the analytical study provided a basis for using 4 fiber layers; however, this decision will be made based on the material characterization tests, taking into consideration the possibility of delamination between the fiber layers.

The study at hand identified great potential in the proposed solution; however, it is necessary to conduct various other analyses, especially regarding the SLS.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

CITATIONS

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